

IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE BEAMS ON AN ELASTIC FOUNDATION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the impact responses of graphite/BMI laminates subjected to low and intermediate velocity impact were investigated. The composite laminates were resting on an elastic foundation with various stiffness values. A novel utilization of a laser interferometry system allowed the real-time indentation to be measured during the impact event. In addition, a PZT sensor mounted to the impactor is used to measure the real-time contact forces. The damage and failure modes were observed through X-ray and optical microscopy. Transient finite element analysis was also conducted to simulate the impact process and the results are compared to experiment.

KEYWORDS: Impact, Composite, Elastic Foundation, Indentation

INTRODUCTION

The performance of composite structures during low-velocity impact events is an important design consideration for aerospace structures. The low through-thickness strength characteristics of laminated composites make them particularly vulnerable to out-of-plane loadings such as transverse impact events. Considerable research has therefore been devoted to understanding the impact response of composite structures [1-3]. Low-velocity impacts occur when the contact duration of the impact event is much larger than the time required for stress waves to propagate to and from the boundaries of the structure. The concept of using quasi-static testing as a means of approximating the low-velocity impact response has been widely accepted [1,4,5]. This is especially true for the overall “global” structural response. The localized response, including the contact behavior, is less understood. However, contact laws derived from quasi-static experiments have been widely used to represent the contact behavior during a low-velocity impact event [6,7]. The inclusion of the elastic foundation into the impact problem may be of particular interest in the study of sandwich structures. The interaction between the facesheet and core material for a sandwich structure has been studied [1,8]. However, in an actual sandwich structure the compressive stresses in the upper facesheet cause buckling which dominates any other failure mechanisms at the impact location [8]. Studies of the impact response of composites on an elastic foundation do not currently exist. The current work addresses this void in the literature by devising an experimental program to generate a comprehensive data set. The presence of the elastic foundation enhances the local contact deformations and isolates the interaction between the specimen and the foundation without the complication of global structural failure due to buckling.

APPROACH

Experiments

An experimental and numerical approach was devised to extract the real-time data and subsequently analyze and understand the results. The composite specimens of interest in this study were made from IM7/5250-4 (Graphite/BMI) pre-preg tape and laminated in two different configurations:

$$\mathbf{L1} = [0_{18}] \quad \mathbf{L2} = [0/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/0]_s$$

Beam specimens 101.6 mm (4 inches) long, 20 mm wide and 3.6 mm thick were cut from 12 inch by 12 inch panels of this material. The zero degree direction corresponds to the length dimension and the 90 degree direction corresponds to the width dimension. The specimens are simply supported along the entire width at each end of the length dimension and are line loaded at the center by a cylindrical-shaped impactor. The elastic foundation material was included as a 12.7 mm thick piece of material beneath the entire specimen. The boundary and loading conditions are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Illustration of boundary and loading conditions in experimental tests

The values of the remaining experimental variables: impactor radius of curvature, elastic foundation material and impact velocity are listed below respectively.

$$\mathbf{R1} = 1.5875 \text{ mm (1/16")}$$

$$\mathbf{R2} = 3.175 \text{ mm (1/8")}$$

$\mathbf{B0}$ = No Foundation

$\mathbf{B1}$ = Silicone Rubber Foundation

$\mathbf{B2}$ = Steel Foundation

$\mathbf{V0}$ = Quasi-static

$\mathbf{V1}$ = 2.5 m/s (nominal)

$\mathbf{V2}$ = 4.0 m/s (nominal)

$\mathbf{V3}$ = 5.5 m/s (nominal)

All subsequent references to a particular specimen configuration will be identified according to the values of each experimental variable, i.e. R1L1B2V1 refers to impactor radius = 1.5875 mm, Uni-directional layup $[0_{18}]$, Rubber foundation material and 2.5 m/s impact velocity.

Numerical Modeling

The modeling portion of this investigation utilized the LSDYNA commercial finite element code. The model ignores any variations through the width dimension due to the line-loading across the entire width, and is thus a 2D model. The impactor is idealized as rigid and the symmetry of the problem allows a half-model to be used. The boundary conditions along with a typical mesh is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Boundary Conditions and Mesh used in F.E.M. Model

In order to accurately obtain the localized contact deformations, the mesh is progressively refined near the contact region. In order to better illustrate this, the mesh is shown only for a portion of the entire beam near the contact point. Results for the global and local structural responses were compared to experiments. Predictions of indentation were only carried out for a purely elastic response. The effect of damage formation on the indentation was therefore not modeled.

GLOBAL STRUCTURAL RESPONSE

The overall structural resistance to bending is manifested in the contact force signal. A more stiff global structural response gives higher contact forces. The detailed local distribution of contact pressure beneath the impactor is not revealed in this signal. Only the global resistance to bending. The force-time signal during the impact is therefore a sufficient representation of the overall global response. The effects of the experimental variables on the force-time response are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Force-time responses showing individual effects of each experimental variable

In each plot all variables are held constant except for the variable of interest. For the purpose of showing trends, values of the variables held constant were chosen, if possible, such that no large-scale damage occurred. This allows a more clear demonstration of the effects of the experimental variables on the global structural response. It should be noted that the effects of the indenter radius on the global response

were not detectable and are therefore left out of Figure 3. The effect of the foundation variable is seen to the left in Figure 3. The presence of the foundation causes a shorter duration impact event with much higher contact forces. The presence of the foundation also decreases the magnitude of the high frequency oscillations of the force signal. The effect of layup is much less pronounced, as seen in the center of Figure 3. Here, the larger bending stiffness of the uni-directional layup causes the contact force to be slightly higher and the impact duration to be slightly less. The effect on the high frequency oscillations is minimal. The effect of impact velocity is shown to the right in Figure 3. Here, the increasing velocity is seen to create larger contact forces with little effect on the impact duration. It should be noted that the highest velocity curve (V4) shows a distinct drop in contact force at 1.4 ms due to the formation of large-scale damage. Every specimen in the test matrix showed large scale damage at the highest velocity (V3). Also, the high frequency oscillations seem to be unaffected by the impact velocity.

A typical comparison of experimental and predicted force-time responses is shown in Figure 4. The modeling results from LSDYNA matched the experiment very well in cases where no large-scale damage occurred. No attempt was made to model the effect of damage on the global structural response. It should be noted that when the contact force reaches zero, this signifies that there is separation between the specimen and impactor. For several tests in this study, multiple separations occurred early in the impact event. The modeling also captures the separation.

Figure 4. Comparison of experimental and predicted force-time response for Specimen R2L1B0V1

STRESSES AND MECHANISTIC FAILURE

Elastic Stress States

In order to understand the global response as well as the mechanisms of failure, the states of stress were computed using LSDYNA. The most influential experimental variable on stresses was the elastic foundation. For simplicity, only the stress results for the uni-directional specimens are presented in this section since the influence of the foundation on the elastic stresses is qualitatively similar for both layups. In addition, the stress states are given at the instant of maximum contact force. The overall trends for the cross-ply specimens were similar. The reader is referred to [8] for a more detailed presentation of the

stress states for the cross-ply laminates. The longitudinal σ_{XX} for specimen R1L1V1 is given for each foundation variable in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Longitudinal σ_{XX} for specimen R1L1V1 at instant of maximum contact force

The entire beam is shown to the left, and a close-up of the same specimen is shown to the right. The plots to the left show the decrease in bending stresses with increasing foundation support. The color scale for the three specimens is not the same. The qualitative distribution of the stresses in each case is what is of interest graphically. The ratio of the maximum compressive σ_{XX} , as compared to the specimen with no foundation, is given as a percentage in the figure. The contact radius (a) is shown to increase with increasing foundation support. However, the maximum σ_{XX} does not monotonically increase with increasing support. The maximum compressive σ_{XX} as compared to the specimen with no foundation is shown to be 98% for the B1 specimen and 228% for the B2 specimen. This is attributed to the competing mechanisms of bending and local contact which both contribute to the compressive σ_{XX} on the top face of the specimen. It is apparent that the presence of foundation support decreases the bending response and increases the local contact response.

A similar comparison of through-thickness σ_{YY} is made for same specimen in Figure 6. A small portion of the beam is shown to the left and a close-up of the contact region is to the right.

Figure 6. Through-thickness σ_{YY} for specimen R1L1V1 at instant of maximum contact force

Here the trend is clearly that the magnitude of compressive σ_{YY} increases markedly with increasing foundation support. Also, the volume of material within the beam which is under compressive σ_{YY} increases with increasing support.

Lastly, the comparison of transverse shear stresses σ_{XY} for the same specimens is shown in Figure 7. Again, a close-up of the specimen is shown to the right for added clarity.

Figure 7. Transverse shear stresses for specimen RIL1V1 at instant of maximum contact force

Again, the trend is a marked increase in the maximum transverse shear stress with increasing foundation support and a larger volume of material which contains non-zero stress values. In both Figures 6 and 7, there is a visible area of color change at one beam thickness away from the centerline. This is due to the tied contact condition used to join two meshes with different densities. The disturbance is not physically real and is considered to be of no consequence to the analysis.

Initial Failure Mode

The initial failure in all specimens in the current study was observed to be a transverse crack emanating from the upper face, within the contact region. An optically magnified picture of this failure mode is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Photograph of initial failure mode

The subsequent growth of the failure depended greatly on the layup and the foundation support. However, the experimental evidence was always consistent with an initial failure in the form of this top-face transverse matrix crack.

Mechanistic Failure Analysis

The initial failure was assumed to be a transverse crack which extended one ply thickness into the material. The x-location of this crack was placed at the point of maximum transverse shear stress. This location was always offset slightly from the exact center. To accomplish this in LSDYNA, the nodes were released along this line. The effects of contact and surface friction were included for this new crack surface.

Inclusion of this initial failure mode into the LSDYNA model showed that it had almost no effect on the stresses at the instant of maximum contact force. However, when the stresses were analyzed at times earlier in the impact, specifically during periods of separation between the specimen and the impactor, the effects of the initial damage were apparent, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Stress states for specimen with initial failure during period of separation

The exact magnitudes of the stress concentrations were not of interest here. We are interested only in a qualitative description of the mechanisms of failure and damage growth. The existence of the tensile σ_{YY} on the outer side of the transverse crack could cause a crack to branch outward at this point. Also, there is a transverse shear stress concentration now evident which could also contribute to crack growth. Neither of these concentrations was evident during periods of full contact, such as that seen at the instant of maximum contact force.

Next, the branching of this transverse crack into a small delamination was modeled. by releasing the nodes for 2 mm along the first ply interface. The resulting σ_{YY} is shown in this scenario in Figure 10. The existence of a stress concentration at the crack tip is evident. The delamination would have a tendency to continue to grow due to a buckling of the top layer.

Figure 10. Transverse y-stresses for specimen with transverse crack and delamination included in model

The behavior of stresses is clearly different for a specimen which exhibits an initial failure and also exhibits separation between the specimen and impactor. The combination of experimental variables which produced separation were examined in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Illustration of separation and its dependence on experimental variables

The two graphs to the left in Figure 11 show the force-time responses for the uni-directional (L1) and cross-ply (L2) specimens with all other variables held constant. The two graphs to the right in Figure 11 show the force-time responses for cross-ply specimens (L2) with no support (B0) and with the silicone rubber support (B1). The likelihood of separation is greatest for the cross-ply specimens with no backing support (L2B0). Damage transcriptions are shown for the cross-ply specimens with no support (L2B0) and with the silicone rubber support (L2B1) in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Damage progression for cross-ply specimens

The damage for the specimens with no backing support starts as a small transverse crack. This crack branches at the first ply interface and simply grows along the interface. The damage for the specimens with the rubber support also start with a small central transverse crack. There is a small branch into a delamination at the first interface. However, there is also a continued growth of damage through the thickness with the largest delaminations occurring near the back face. The overall state of damage is much less for the cross-ply specimen with no support.

Damage transcriptions for the uni-directional specimens with no support (L1B0) and with the silicone rubber support (L1B1) are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Damage progression for uni-directional specimens

The damage for the specimens with no foundation starts as a small transverse crack. This crack grows through the thickness and branches at different points along the depth. Finally, at the largest velocity, the transverse crack extends through the entire thickness and causes complete failure of the specimen into 2 parts. The damage for the specimens with the rubber foundation starts as a small transverse crack. This crack grows along the thickness and branches at various depths. However, even at the largest velocity the transverse crack does not grow through the thickness of the specimen. This may be explained by considering the effect of the foundation. The foundation absorbs some of the impact energy whereas in the case of no foundation, all the impact energy must be absorbed in bending strain energy. As the transverse crack grows through the thickness, there is less beam thickness near the center to resist the same bending loads transferred by the impactor. The result is catastrophic and likely unstable failure at some critical depth of the transverse crack. When there is a foundation present, the foundation itself resists the impact loads directly, thereby decreasing the overall dependence on the beam's bending strain energy. As a transverse crack grows through the depth, the foundation can now accept more of the impact loads as the beam is weakened. This would make it less likely that a crack would grow in an unstable manner through the entire thickness.

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental study showed a wide range of structural responses and damage development. Subsequent analysis showed that LSDYNA could adequately predict the elastic force-time response and the stress analysis provided insight into the mechanistic failure. The existence of an elastic foundation decreased the overall damage resistance for cross-ply specimens and increased the overall damage resistance for uni-directional specimens. It is also postulated that the presence of the foundation for uni-directional specimens changes the failure from an unstable transverse crack growth to a stable growth of the transverse crack along with branching delaminations. Although the damage development shown in this study was consistent with the mechanistic arguments presented, further work needs to be done in this area to further validate these assertions. Modeling which goes beyond a 2D ply-level analysis is also suggested as a means of further identifying the mechanisms present.

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